

Examining the Effect of Vocational Training, Competency, and Job Satisfaction on Employee Productivity: Evidence from Indonesia

Yanthy Herawaty Purnama, Didin Hikmah Perkasa, Hegar Harini

Article Info	Abstract
<p><i>Article History</i></p> <p>Received: February 01, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: April 18, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Competence, Job satisfaction, Job training, Work productivity</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4699722</p>	<p><i>This research was conducted to determine the effect of job training, competence, and job satisfaction on work productivity. Quantitative descriptive method was employed. The sample of this research is 50 employees of Hotel 88 Jakarta, branch of Mangga Besar 120. The collected data were analyzed using statistical computation in the form of multiple linear regression tests. The results of this study indicated that partially job training and job satisfaction variables affect work productivity of employees at Hotel 88 Jakarta, branch of Mangga Besar 120. This was statistically proven from the results of the partial test (t-test) pointing out the significant effect of the two independent variables.</i></p>

Introduction

The growth of the tourism and hospitality industry globally is on the rise. This is seen not only because tourists are becoming more aware of their preferences and demands, but also because the attractiveness of new destinations is becoming more and more spread out in the world. More hotels get interconnected such as Accor, Swiss-belhotel, Archipelago Internasional, Santika Indonesia, Inter Continental Hotels Group, Tauzia Management, and Waringin Hospitality.

Hotels that want to survive to operate must have more values to distinguish them from other companies. The added value offered will further provide certainty for loyal and potential customers to transact again. Due to the character of hospitality as a service industry, hotels should provide ultimate product and services to their customers. The design of buildings, interiors and exteriors of hotel rooms, restaurants, as well as meeting rooms or ballrooms, the atmosphere created in the hotel rooms, restaurants and the food and beverages that are sold along with all existing facilities are examples of products being sold. While the services provided are the hospitality and skills of hotel employees in serving their customers, considering that these factors can influence guests' preference to stay.

Besides the aforementioned factors, one thing to influence the success of a company or an organization in achieving its goals is employee work effectiveness. Employees are an important resource that determines the success of an organization. In effort to attain the organizational goals effectively, working effectiveness in workplace is needed.

Effective working begins with employee productivity that supports company management. Productivity is pivotal due to its great supports to the success of an organization in gaining profits (Bellet et al., 2019; Muminović & Barać, 2015). Principally, work productivity is a measurement to determine additional value of employees for their organization (Gómez-Mejía et al., 2012). People whose high productivity shall contribute meaningful values to their companies. Robbins & Judge (2017) see work productivity in its connection with efficiency and effectiveness standard at workplace. Sedarmayanti (2017) even underlines that work productivity shall contribute to working environment.

However, it was reported a decrease of employee productivity in the hotel. It was concluded from the data of occupancy as one of the hotel productivity indicators. Getting worse, the decrease was stated to continually take place for a couple of years. On this ground, the action of advancing the employee productivity is decisive to take.

To foster employee productivity or performance, companies must pay attention to a number of factors. Training, competence and job satisfaction are trusted to give significant impact on employee work productivity as highlighted by a number of studies.

First, training as an effort to improve current and future performance (Rivai & Sagala, 2011) to carry out jobs has been proven to result in skill, ability, and knowledge which further impacts on employee organizational performance (Daniel, 2018). As emphasized by Dessler (2017), training is intended for employees to carry out their jobs. Research of Rahardianto et al. (2017) to the employees of a private company in Indonesia noticed that compensation, welfare benefits, education and training give significant influence on the employees' work productivity. Another research conducted by Kanapathipillai & Azam (2020) in a telecommunication company of Malaysia has indicated that training program is significantly related to job performance and satisfaction. Training program was also reported to give greater benefit in terms of work satisfaction development, positive feedback, quality output achievement, and career development (Halawi & Haydar, 2018).

The second factor believed to affect work productivity is competence. Competence, which is claimed as basic characteristics consisting of knowledge, skills, ability, and attitude, is predicted to have mutual connection with productivity at work (Spencer & Spencer, 1993). The study of Heriyanto et al. (2018) found out how competence directly affects work performance of tax office employees. It was further claimed that their competence determines their service to taxpayers. Competence was also detected to give huge impact on lecturers' performance when providing academic service to students (Utama et al., 2017). Manani & Ngui (2019) found out suggestive potential of competence to upgrade employee job performance. Therefore, competence renewal is highly recommended.

The last factor to predict work productivity is job satisfaction. Employees whose high satisfactory feeling about their job tends to work more productively which at the end, it will positively impact on the achievement of company goals. Job satisfaction has to do with someone's level of positive or negative feeling about his/her job (Schermerhorn Jr et al., 2010), favorable and unfavorable (Newstrom & Davis, 2015), in which it is typically inter-related in organizational behavior (Kondalkar, 2007) and influences productivity in a positive way (Robbins & Judge, 2017). Research of Embuldeniya (2017) even claimed that work satisfaction is the most influencing predictor on employee productivity. Positive relation between job satisfaction and work productivity was also revealed by Okulova (2018) and Chehrazi & Shafizadeh (2016).

Each of the above mentioned research were conducted to see how every factor affects work productivity. The present study then attempts to unite the variables and conduct research in one single time to see how training, competence, and job satisfaction give impact on employee work productivity.

Method

The research method used is quantitative research methods with a causal research design, namely to determine the relationship between work motivation variables and work productivity. According to Sugiyono (2013) and Juanamasta et al. (2019), causal is a relationship where the independent variable affects the dependent variable. Thus the data collected by researchers through data collection techniques in this study were to conduct observations and surveys directly on the research object, namely employees of PT Hero Supermarket Plc, Guardian Division Branch of Regional South Jakarta 2.

Population and samples, according to Sugiyono (2014) states that population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics that are determined by researchers to be studied and then draw conclusions. The population in this study were all employees who worked at hotel 88, amounting to 50 people. Furthermore, the research sample, according to Sugiyono (2014), the sample is part of the number and characteristics of the population. Determination of the sample using saturated sampling. Sugiyono (2014) argues that the saturated sampling technique is a sampling technique when all members of the population are used as samples. The samples used were 50 employees of Hotel 88 Mangga Besar 120.

The data collection techniques used by the authors in this study are: 1). Distribution of Questionnaires. According to Sugiyono (2013: 142), questionnaires are a data collection technique which is done by giving a set of questions or written statements to respondents to answer. 2). Interview technique, interview technique is data collection which is done by asking directly to informants regarding the data needed. According to Subagyo (2011) Interview is an activity carried out to obtain information directly by expressing questions to the respondents. Interview means face to face between the interviewer (s) and the respondent, and the activities are carried out orally"

Data analysis methods used are: 1). Descriptive Statistical Test, 2) Data Quality Test which consists of a) validity test and b) reliability test, 3). The Classical Assumption Test consists of a) normality test, b) multicollinearity test and c) heteroscedasticity test. 4). Multiple Regression Analysis Method 5). Hypothesis testing which includes a) Test of the coefficient of determination (R^2) b) Simultaneous significance test (f test) c) Partial significance test (t test).

Results and Discussion

Results

Respondent Characteristics

The research sample was employees of Hotel 88 Jakarta branch of Mangga Besar Raya No. 120, Sawah Besar, Central Jakarta, totalling 50 people. As a preliminary analysis, a review of the respondents' identity data is initially administered. Presentation of data regarding the characteristics of the respondents is presented as follows.

Description of Respondents by Gender

Based on the research results, it is obtained a description of the gender of the respondents which can be seen in table 4.1 as follows:

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Male	33	66.0	66.0	66.0
Female	17	34.0	34.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Based on table 4.1 above, it can be seen that the number of male respondents are 33 people or 66.0% and female respondents are 17 people or 34.0%. Thus it can be concluded that in this study most of the respondents at Hotel 88 Jakarta Mangga Besar 120 are male.

Description of Respondents by Age

Based on the results of the study, a description of the age of the respondents was obtained which can be seen in table 4.2 as follows:

Table 2. Characteristics of Respondents by Age

Age	Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
17 – 24	10	20.0	20.0	20.0
25 - 29	19	38.0	38.0	58.0
30-34	18	36.0	36.0	94.0
> 35	3	6.0	6.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Based on table 4.2, it can be seen that the number of respondents who filled out this questionnaire. Respondents aged 17-24 were 10 people or 20%, aged 25-29 were 19 people or 38.0%, aged 30-34 were 18 people or 36.0% and ages > 35 were 3 or 6 %. Thus it can be concluded that in this study most of the respondents at Hotel 88 Jakarta Mangga Besar 120 were 25-29 years old.

Results of Descriptive Statistics Test

Descriptive statistics are statistics that are used to analyze data that has been collected as a result of it or without the intention of making generally accepted conclusions.

Results of Data Quality Test

Results of the Validity Test

The results of calculations that have been carried out for the variable indicators of Job Training, Competence and Job Satisfaction are greater than 0.278 so it can be concluded that the variable indicator for Job Performance Assessment is said to be valid. The results of the reliability test carried out with the SPSS program found that the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient for the Job Training Variable was greater than 0.6, namely 0.648, the Competency Variable was greater than 0.6, namely 0.784, the Job Satisfaction Variable was greater than 0.6, which was equal to 0.888, and the Work Productivity Variable is greater than 0.6 which is equal to 0.852. Thus it can be concluded that the four variables are reliable

Results of the Classical Assumption Test

Normality test

The normality test aims to test whether in the regression model, the independent variable has a normal distribution or not

Table 3. Results of Normality Test One-Sample Kolmogorov Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		50
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	32.5800000
Most Extreme Differences	Std. Deviation	2.95083017
	Absolute	.081
	Positive	.063
	Negative	-.081
Test Statistic		.081
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200c,d

Based on the results of data processing on SPSS in table 4.15 above, it can be seen that all X1 (Job Training), X2 (Competency), X3 (Job Satisfaction), and Y (Work Productivity) variables have Asymp values. Sig. (2-tailed) of 0.200 greater than 0.05, it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed.

Multicolliniarity Test

Table 4. Multicollinearity Test

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)		
Job Training	.653	1.531
Competence	.641	1.560
Job satisfaction	.750	1.333

Based on table 4:16 above, it shows that the effect of tolerance of each independent variable, namely Job Training (X1) is 0.653, Competence (X2) is 0.641 and Job Satisfaction (X3) is 0.750. From the results of the variance inflation factor (VIF) output, it is known that each independent variable, namely Job Training (X1) is 1.531, Competence (X2) is 1.560, and Job Satisfaction (X3) is 1.333. Thus, the three independent variables have

a tolerance value ≥ 0.10 and a VIF value ≤ 10 so it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity between the independent variables.

Result of Heteroscedasticity Test

Figure 1. Results of the Heteroscedasticity Test

From the scatterplot graphic image above, it appears that the dots spread out randomly and do not form a certain pattern and are spread either above or below the 0 (zero) number on the Y axis. Thus, it can be concluded that heteroscedasticity does not occur. If there is a certain pattern such as the existing dots forming a certain regular pattern (wavy, widening then narrowing), and if there is no clear pattern and dots that spread above and below the zero on the Y axis, then there is no heteroscedasticity.

Results of Multiple Linear Regression Test

Table 4.5 Results of Multiple Linear Regression Test

Coefficients					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	10.411	4.934		2.110	.040
Job Training	.352	.161	.291	2.181	.034
Competence	-.054	.223	-.033	-.244	.809
Job satisfaction	.553	.132	.522	4.188	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Work Productivity

Based on the results of data processing using SPSS in table 4:14 above, it can be obtained the formulation of multiple linear regression equations for the independent variables (Job Training, Competence, Job Satisfaction) on the dependent variable (Work Productivity) as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + e$$

$$Y = 10,411 + 0,352 X_1 - 0,054 X_2 + 0,553 X_3 + e$$

The regression equation has the following meanings:

- The regression coefficient (X_1) has a t value of 2.181. The results show that the job training variable has a positive effect on the work productivity of the employees of Hotel 88 Jakarta, branch of Mangga Besar 120, in other words if the job training variable is increased by one unit, the work productivity of the employees will increase by 2,181. From these results it can be concluded that job training that is properly implemented will increase employee productivity.
- The regression coefficient (X_2) has a t value of -0.244. The results show that the competency variable has a negative effect on the work productivity of employees at Hotel 88 Jakarta, branch of Mangga Besar 120, in other words, if the competency variable is increased by one unit, the employee work productivity will decrease by 0.244. From these results it can be concluded that the competencies possessed by employees are not in accordance with the competencies needed by the organization.
- The regression coefficient (X_3) has a t value of 4.188. The results show that the job satisfaction variable has a positive effect on the work productivity of the employees of Hotel 88 Jakarta, branch of Mangga

Besar 120, in other words, if the job satisfaction variable is increased by one unit, the work productivity of the employees will increase by 4,188. From these results it can be concluded that job satisfaction fulfilled will increase employee productivity.

Model Accuracy Test

Determination Coefficient Test (R²)

The coefficient of determination is used to find out how much the independent variables have an influence on the dependent variable. The coefficient of determination used adjusted R square which can be seen in the following table:

Table 6. Results of the determination coefficient test (R²)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin Waston
1	.681 ^a	.464	.429	3.275	2.240

a. Predictors: (Constant), Job Satisfaction, Competence, Job Training.

b. Dependent Variable: Work productivity

Based on table 4.17, it is known that the coefficient of determination (adjusted R²) is 0.429, which means 42.9%, which means that the contribution of Work Productivity can be explained by the three independent variables, namely Job Training, Competence, and Job Satisfaction. So the remaining 57.1% is explained by other variables not examined in this study.

Simultaneous Significance Test (F test)

The F statistical test shows whether the independent variables referred to in the model have a joint influence on the dependent variable. The results of the F statistical test can be seen in the following 4:18 table:

Table 7. Results of Model Accuracy Test (Statistical Test F) ANOVAa

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	426.663	3	142.221	13.256	.000b
	Residual	493.517	46	10.729		
	Total	920.180	49			

a. Dependent Variable: Work productivity

b. Predictors: (Constant), Job Satisfaction, Competence, Job Training

Based on Table 4.18, it can be seen that the probability value sig 0.000 means that the probability value is smaller than 0.05, so the model is accepted, thus it can be concluded that Job Training, Competence, and Job Satisfaction together have an effect on Work Productivity.

Test of Significance of Individual Parameters (T test)

The t statistical test basically shows how far the influence of one explanatory or independent variable individually in explaining the variation in the dependent variable. Decision making can be done by looking at probability. If the probability or significance > 0.05 then Ho is accepted and Ha is rejected and if the probability or significance < 0.05 then Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted.

Table 8. Results of Partial Significance Accuracy Test (T test) Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			

1 (Constant)	10.411	4.934		2.110	.040
Job Training	.352	.161	.291	2.181	.034
Competence	-.054	.223	-.033	-.244	.809
Job satisfaction					
	.553	.132	.522	4.118	.000

Dependent Variable: Work productivity

From the table above, the following conclusions can be concluded:

a. Hypothesis Test of Job Training on Work Productivity

Based on table 4:19, the probability of sig of Job Training is 0.034 smaller than 0.05, so that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted, it can be stated that partially Job Training (X1) has a significant effect on Work Productivity (Y).

b. Competency Hypothesis Test on Work Productivity

Based on table 4:19 the probability of sig Competence is 0.809 greater than 0.05, so that Ho is accepted and Ha is rejected, it can be stated partially Competence (X2) has no significant and negative effect on Work Productivity (Y).

c. Hypothesis Test of the Effect of Job Satisfaction on Work Productivity

Based on table 4:19, the probability of job satisfaction is 0,000 smaller than 0.05, so that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted, it can be stated partially Job Satisfaction (X3) has a significant effect on Work Productivity (Y).

Discussion

The Effect of Job Training on Work Productivity

Based on the results of the t test calculation shows that training has an influence on work productivity at Hotel 88 Jakarta Mangga Besar 120. This is because the company is still lacking in job training so as to increase the skills and knowledge of employees are lacking. This finding is supported by the theory of Hasibuan (2014) which states that the implementation of training programs shapes and improves the skills and knowledge of employees, so it is hoped that the more frequent training programs are implemented, the higher the level of productivity.

The result of this study in in congruence with Sudarjat's research (2015) and Budiarta et al. (2015) in which job training has a positive and significant effect on work productivity. The results of this study also corroborate the research conducted by Karima et al. (2018) to a number of banking employees at public regional bank owned by provincial governance in Makassar, South Sulawesi, Indonesia. The results of the study concluded that training had a positive and significant effect on the work productivity of employees. Positive and significant effect of education and training on employee performance have also been proven by Idris (2018) to employees working at government department of disaster management in Indonesia. Corresponding to the present research finding, a survey on health sector employees in Uganda have resulted in similar influence (Sendawula et al., 2018).

To be more specific, the present research finding is in harmony with what found by Abdullahi et al. (2018) in a public university in Nigeria, that training including method, design and its style of delivery significantly impacts employee productivity. Underlining the significant outcome of training, Alnawfleh (2020) has statistically compared the difference of how employees, who had already got trained, show much better performance compared to those who had not.

Accordingly, it is certain that organizing training for the hotel employees is urgent to perform. More training held are expected to enhance their basic knowledge, skill, and ability. At the end, the enhancement shall give contribution to meet the hotel ultimate target, goals and profit.

The Effect of Competence on Work Productivity

Based on the results of the t-test calculation, it shows that competence has no effect on work productivity at Hotel 88 Jakarta Mangga Besar 120. This is because the competencies possessed by employees are good enough,

but the company wants to further improve competencies in the hospitality sector owned by employees to increase work productivity of hotel employees 88 Jakarta Mangga Besar 120, according to Simanjuntak (2005), who states that individual performance is influenced by competency factors, the higher the employee's competence, the higher the performance he achieves (Parukawa, 2014). Sujana (2012) acknowledged that higher competence of employees addressing the job demand shall direct to much higher performance. This is predicted to occur as competent employees have ability and willingness to overcome the encountered problems, perform job with calm and confidence, view job as an obligation to perform sincerely, and openly improve self-quality by learning.

The present research finding does not correspond to a number of relevant research. Having surveyed lecturers working in private higher education institutions in Aceh, Utama et al. (2017) reported that competence gives significant direct influence on the productivity of private lecturers. The analysis of competence effect on productivity to employees of one state owned company in West Java also exhibit significant findings (Siswandy & Saragih, 2017). Tax office officers' performance in Malang, Central Java, Indonesia, was also determined by their competence (Heriyanto et al., 2018). A survey to a number of bankers in one public bank branch also demonstrated positive and significant result of competence on work performance (Nusa et al., 2020). Detailing the essence of training, a recent study conducted by Martini et al. (2020) unveiled how competence comprising of knowledge, skills, and attitudes significantly and positively impact on employee commitment and performance or productivity (Abubakar, 2018).

Howbeit, equipping the hotel employees with adequate competence both theoretically and practically should be promoted. Competent and qualified employees provide the customers with great assistance that certainly will catch their attention to come and stay in the hotel.

The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Work Productivity

Based on the results of the t-test calculation, it shows that job satisfaction has an influence on work productivity at Hotel 88 Jakarta Mangga Besar 120. This is because the company has not fulfilled employee job satisfaction due to the absence of promotion, so that employees who have worked for a long time feel bored with lower positions and causes a decrease in work productivity.

The result of this study is commensurable with the following studies. Adiwinata (2014), and Sriyono & Lestari (2013) presented the findings that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on work productivity. The results of this study also strengthen the research conducted by Osiani (2015) to workers at a private company in an airport concluding that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee work productivity. Surveying employees in manufacturing industries, Shobe (2018) came to a conclusion that job satisfaction is empirically proven to have a strong connection with job performance and employees' work output. Similar result was also discovered at one of the biggest private companies in UK telecommunication sector, establishing the validity that happy feeling gives more leverage for labours to work and boost more sales (Bellet et al., 2019).

To go further, Said et al. (2017) have shown in their study that fulfilled job satisfaction will lead to an increase in employee work productivity which will also have a positive impact on the achievement of company goals. Another study found out college teaching personnel perform more productive works once their job grants them satisfactory feeling (MacUtay, 2020). The better performance can be measured from how workers deal with their duties; satisfied workers show more responsibility of their jobs (Dziuba et al., 2020). Uniquely, a significant relation between job satisfaction and performance has already tied these two variables in a cycle cause relationship (Alromaihi et al., 2017), in which job satisfaction directs to work performance and vice versa.

Ultimately, the hotel employee job satisfaction will bring favorable tendency to their productivity or performance. To that end, careful analysis and consideration on the factors leading to the employee job satisfaction should be taken into account by the hotel management.

Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussion in the previous chapter regarding the effect of Job Training, Competence, and Job Satisfaction on Work Productivity at Hotel 88 Magga Besar 120, the conclusions in this study are as follows: job training affects work productivity and job satisfaction has an effect on work productivity while competence has no effect on work productivity.

Recommendations

The present study findings signify that the hotel employees' productivity is mostly impacted by vocational training and job satisfaction. On this ground, the hotel management effort to equip the employees with sufficient trainings is highly suggested. Providing satisfactory work environment to enhance the employees' job satisfaction should also be taken into consideration.

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Author Information

Yanthy Herawaty Purnama

Universitas Dian Nusantara,
 Jl. Tanjung Duren Barat 2 No.1 Rt. 1/Rw.5 Tjg Duren
 Utara, Kec. Grogol, Petamburan, Jakarta Barat, Daerah
 Khusus Ibukota Jakarta 11470

Didin Hikmah Perkasa

Universitas Dian Nusantara,
 Jl. Tanjung Duren Barat 2 No.1 Rt. 1/Rw.5 Tjg Duren
 Utara, Kec. Grogol, Petamburan, Jakarta Barat, Daerah
 Khusus Ibukota Jakarta 11470

Hegar Harini

STKIP Kusuma Negara
 Jl. Raya Bogor Km.24 Cijantung, Jakarta Timur, 13770
